

^{13}C Nmr Spectra of Acutangulic and Tangulic Acids from *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn.

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^{13}C nmr spectra of acutangulic and tangulic acids are now presented in support of the structures 1 and 2 proposed earlier. The effect of the 18β -hydroxyl on the C12-13 olefinic bond is discussed.

FROM the leaves of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn., two rare triterpene carboxylic acids, acutangulic and tangulic acids (1 and 2) were isolated in these laboratories¹. The former was shown to be $2\alpha, 3\beta, 18\beta$ -trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (1), and the latter $2\alpha, 3\beta, 18\beta$ -trihydroxyolean-12-en-23,28-dioic acid (2). These assignments were supported by ^1H nmr, mass spectra and chemical evidence. The configuration of the 18 -hydroxyl was suggested to be β -equatorial as both acids failed to give a triacetate or a lactone even under forced conditions. To confirm the above structures, ^{13}C nmr spectra of their diacetates were secured and results presented here.

Experimental

The leaves (2 kg) of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn. were successively extracted with hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol. Separation of the individual components from the above extracts was achieved by fractional crystallisation followed by column chromatography on silica gel G as reported earlier¹. γ -sitosterol, β -sitosterol, β -D(+)-glucopyranoside, barringtonic acid, β -amyrin, oleanolic acid, tangulic acid and acutangulic acid were identified in the usual manner (m.m.p., ir, and ^1H nmr).

The diacetates of acutangulic and tangulic acids were prepared by the action of $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$ at 100° . The ^{13}C nmr spectra of these diacetates were recorded on Varian spectrometer at 67.89 MHz in d_6 -DMSO with TMS as internal standard and the assignments are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Like maslinic acid (3), the acutangulic and tangulic acids (1 and 2) are $2\alpha, 3\beta$ -diols and their ^{13}C nmr spectra resemble very closely. Introduction of an equatorial hydroxyl at C-2 has a marked downfield shift of about δ 8.2 on C-1 in 1 and 2, (C-1, δ 46.94, 46.97) as in methyl maslinate (C-1, δ 46.4), compared to that of methyl oleanolate² (C-1, δ 38.2). Similar correspondance of the C-4 and C-10 shifts in 1 and 2 are also observed with those of methyl maslinate (3).

TABLE 1— ^{13}C NMR SPECTRA

	Methyl maslinate* (3) ODCl ₃	Acutangulic acid (1) diacetate d_6 -DMSO	Tangulic acid (2) diacetate d_6 -DMSO
C-1	46.4	46.94	46.97
C-2	60.5	71.77	71.74
C-3	78.9	79.95	78.25
C-4	39.1	38.76	38.59
C-5	55.8	54.18	49.01
C-6	18.3	17.92	19.56
C-7	32.6	32.40	32.55
C-8	39.1	37.95	38.10
C-9	47.5	46.41	46.18
C-10	38.3	38.94	38.95
C-11	23.1	23.87	23.87
C-12	124.0	126.80	126.50
C-13	143.6	138.73	138.69
C-14	41.7	44.53	43.96
C-15	27.6	27.50	25.92
C-16	23.5	23.16	23.25
C-17	46.6	54.07	54.95
C-18	41.3	69.19	69.13
C-19	45.8	58.16	58.29
C-20	30.7	28.99	28.09
C-21	38.8	32.40	32.55
C-22	32.8	28.08	28.09
C-23	28.6	27.96	174.47
C-24	16.8	17.33	25.27
C-25	16.8	16.56	16.46
C-26	16.8	16.15	16.15
C-27	26.0	26.25	26.35
C-28	178.0	178.75	178.75
C-29	33.1	37.14	37.11
C-30	23.5	23.16	23.78
OH ₁ COO	—	20.16, 169.92	20.58, 170.23
OH ₂ COO	—	20.65, 169.87	20.68, 169.51

- 1 $\text{R}_1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \beta\text{-OH}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 2 $\text{R}_1 = \text{COOH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \beta\text{-OH}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 3 $\text{R}_1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$
 4 $\text{R}_1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \alpha\text{-OH}$.

TABLE 2

	Methyl oleanolate	Methyl maslinate ^a	Arjunic acid ^a	8,19-diol 28-COOMe ^a	Acutangulic acid diacetate DMSO	Tangulic acid diacetate DMSO
	CDCl_3	CDCl_3	DMSO	CDCl_3	DMSO	DMSO
C-12	121.5	122.0	123.4	126.9	120.9	126.52
C-13	144.9	148.6	144.9	138.7	138.73	138.69

In tangulic acid (2) diacetate^a, replacement of 23 α -equatorial methyl by a carboxyl caused a marked downfield shift of 15.84 ppm in C-4 resonance (δ 54.59) compared to δ 38.75 of C-4 in the acutangulic acid diacetate. This carboxyl has the expected γ -effect, i.e. δ +1.5 on C-3 and +5.12 ppm on C-5, comparable to those recorded for pimara-diene and pimarinic acid^{5,6}.

The olefinic carbons, C-12 and C-13, appeared at δ 126.80 and 138.73 for 1 and at 126.52 and 138.69 for 2, significantly different from those of methyl maslinate or methyl oleanolate (Table 2) in which the D/E ring-junction is known to be *cis*. It is clear that the 18 β -equatorial hydroxyl of 1 and 2 caused a prominent downfield shift of δ 4.8 of C-12 but an equal and opposite effect is experienced by C-13.

The effect of hydroxyl on 12-13 olefinic bond in oleanenes and ursenes was studied by Lewis *et al.*⁷ with the help of ^{13}C nmr. He records that the 19-hydroxyl in oleanenes, if equatorial, exerts the same influence as the 19 β -methyl in ursenes (Table 2) and, therefore, concludes that the chemical shift change is due to the steric influence of 19 β -hydroxyl. The 19 α -hydroxyl of oleanenes has only a minor effect.

In the acutangulic acid and tangulic acid, the effect of 18 β -hydroxyl is very similar to that of 19 β -hydroxyl. This may not be taken to be entirely due to the steric influence in view of the polar character of the hydroxyl, unlike the 19 β -methyl of the ursenes. On a close examination of the molecular models (constructed out of dreiding models) the 18 β -hydroxyl is equidistant between C-12 and C-13 approximately within 2.1 Å. In another conformation, this hydroxyl approaches C-12 within 1.9 Å and C-13 within 2.18 Å approximately. This

is quite comparable to that of 19 β -hydroxyl which approaches C-12 or C-13 within approximately 2.1 Å and 2.5 Å, respectively. Thus, the 18 β - and 19 β -hydroxyls are quite close to the π electron system of 12-13 bond (D/E *cis*) and, therefore, possess similar effect on C-12 and C-13, the former being deshielded by about δ 4.8 to 5.3 and the latter shielded by about δ 4.9 to 6.2 (*cf.* Ref. 8).

It is significant to record in this connection that in arjunic acid (4)⁴, the 19 α -axial hydroxyl does not have any recognisable effect on C-12 or C-13. If D/E ring is *trans*, the 18-hydroxyl assumes $\leftarrow$ -axial configuration and is far removed from C-12 or C-13 and leaves them unaffected, thus confirming the 18 β -hydroxyl in acutangulic and tangulic acids (1 and 2).

The *cis* D/E junction is further supported by the C-17 resonances (δ 54.07 in 1 and 54.95 in 2) around 8 ppm downfield compared to that of methyl maslinate (δ 46.6). The remaining assignments are entirely in agreement with the structures proposed for these acids (1 and 2).

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^a Barrigenic acid^a from the fruits is the 19 β -hydroxy isomer and barrinic acid^b from the branch wood is 19 α -hydroxy isomer. Both differ extensively from 2.

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